

Volume 9, Number 1, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Geo studies is a peer-reviewed journal, published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The purpose of the journal is to make quickly available the fruits of Geography related researches with emphasis on the tropical environment. Contributions are therefore invited from any part of the broad field constituted by geographical or spatial sciences and studies in their economic, political, social and policy dimensions. Research may be broadly defined, but must be sound in methodology, critical, entertaining, analytical, make contribution to existing knowledge and conclusions drawn must address contemporary issues.

CALL FOR PAPERS

We cordially request the submission of original papers for possible inclusion in the forthcoming issue of GEO-STUDIES FORUM (ISSN 1596-4116), published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin.

AREAS OF INTEREST

This scholarly peer-reviewed journal accepts original articles covering, but not limited to, the following areas:

- Geography
- Environmental Management
- Climate Science
- Soil Science
- Water Resources Management
- Biogeography
- Indigenous Knowledge System

- Urban and Regional Planning
- Transport Studies
- Demography
- Tourism Studies
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Disaster Risk Management

GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSION

MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION

- Language: British English
- Format: Microsoft Word (MS)
- Paper Size: A4
- Font: Times New Roman
- Font Size: 12
- Line Spacing: Double
- Page Limit: 20 pages (excluding references)
- Abstract: Not more than 250 words, single-spaced
- Keywords: 4-5

MANUSCRIPT STRUCTURE

- Title
- Authors' names and affiliations (including emails of all authors, with the corresponding author clearly indicated)
- Abstract
- Introduction
- Methodology
- Findings
- Conclusion
- Recommendations

REFERENCES

- Format: APA
- Line Spacing: Single with hanging indent
- Space between references: 12 pt

SUBMISSION

- Submit to:
geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng
- Include evidence of payment of nonrefundable assessment fee of ₦10,000 (Ten thousand Naira only)

PUBLICATION FEE

Upon acceptance, submit the reviewed manuscript with evidence of payment of a non-refundable fee of ₦20,000 (Twenty thousand Naira only)

BANK DETAILS

- **Account Name:** GEOSTUDIES FORUM
- **Account Number:** 2324256060
- **Bank:** UBA

CONTENTS

ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE STRATEGIES EMPLOYED BY HERDERS IN THE PROVISION OF FODDER FOR LIVESTOCK IN THE GRAZING RESERVES OF NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA <i>Abubakar Hassan</i>	1 - 12
SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF WETLAND DEGRADATION: A REVIEW <i>Isaiah S. Akoteyon, Jimoh O. Saka, & Jolaade M. Olatunbosun</i>	13 - 38
ASSESSING INFLUENCE OF FLOODING ON SOIL TEXTURE IN AGWAN DODO IN GWAGWALADA AREA COUNCIL, ABUJA <i>Hadiza Abubakar Ahmad</i>	29 - 42
ASSESSMENT OF THE CAUSES AND STRATEGIES OF CONTROLLING SLUM DEVELOPMENT IN MARARABA, KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Usman Abubakar Oseshi, A. I. Abdullahi, and I. Z. Ismail</i>	43 - 52
CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN SHOMOLU LGA, LAGOS, NIGERIA <i>Grace Ometere Abu, Rayleigh Dada Abu, Esther Englama, and Henry Usiobaifo Agbebaku</i>	53 - 70
CLIMATIC VARIABILITY AND CHANGE IN THE HOLOCENE EPOCH IN WEST AFRICA: A DISCUSSION OF PALEOENVIRONMENTAL AND PALEOCLIMATIC CHANGES IN THE PAST 10,000 YEARS <i>TUBI, Paul-Kolade and OLATUNDE, Adewale</i>	71 - 81
DISTANCE – FROM –LEACH PIT AND QUALITY OF SHALLOW GROUNDWATER IN SELECTED WARDS OF ILORIN SOUTH LGA, ILORIN, NIGERIA <i>Balogun, Yekeen Idowu</i>	82 - 102
ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF SPATIO-SEASONAL VARIATION OF CLIMATIC PATTERN ON AIR POLLUTANT CONCENTRATION IN JALINGO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, TARABA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Paulinus Ifeanyi Chukwu, Danjuma Ijudigal Garandi and Mohammed Sayd Dzarma</i>	103 - 115

EDITORIAL BOARD

- Dr I.O Orire:** orire.io@unilorin.edu.ng
08032942992
- Prof. L.T. Ajibade:** edabijalt@unilprin.edu.ng
08075251963
- Dr B.A. Usman:** usman.ba@unilorin.edu.ng
08036909201
- Dr Toluwalope M. Agaja:** agaja.tm@unilorin.edu.ng
07032329906
- Prof. Roda M. Olanrewaju:** lamoji@unilorin.edu.ng
08057674931
- Prof. Afolabi M. Tunde:** afolabi@unilorin.edu.ng
08038540145

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

- Prof. Gbadegesin, A. S. -** Dept. of Geography, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
08033661346
adeniyig55@gmail.com
- Prof. Abdullahi, John -** Dept of Geography, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.
08036821438
drajohn74@gmail.com
- Prof. Ogunbodede, E. Funlayo -** Dept. of Geography & Planning Sciences, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba, Ondo State.
08077860313
emmanuel.ogunbodede@aaua.edu.ng
- Prof. Akoteyon, I. S. -** Dept. of Environmental Management, Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos State. 08023161616
isaiah.akoteyon@lasu.edu

PATRON

- Prof. Adedayo, A. F. (Rtd.) -** Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

JOURNAL'S CONTACTS

Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Emails: geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng, edabijalt@unilorin.edu.ng

Website: Visit the journal website at: Geo-Studies Forum

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF WETLAND DEGRADATION: A REVIEW

*Isaiah S. AKOTEYON¹, Jimoh O. SAKA² & Jolaade M. OLATUNBOSUN³

¹Department of Environmental Management, Lagos State University

²Department of Economics, Lagos State University

³Centre for Agroecology Water and Resilience, Coventry University

*Corresponding Author's Email: sewanuakot@gmail.com

Abstract: *The degradation of wetland resources throughout the world is approaching an alarming proportion due to several factors such as population explosion, climate change, anthropogenic activities, hydrological perturbation, and pollution among others. The review examined the socio-economic impacts of wetland degradation and sediment quality, and identified the advantages of wetland to include fuel, wood production, cultivation of food crop and vegetable and flood control in the urban area while tourism and recreation benefits abound in the rural settlements. The predominant factors responsible for wetland degradation include; poor conservation management practices, industrial revolution, mining and dredging activities, lack of accurate data, inconsistencies and poor enforcement of government policies and high poverty rate. The major socio-economic impacts of wetland degradation indicate that, land subsidence, rise in water borne diseases, therapeutic health value, drainage of soil improvement, increase in carbon dioxide emission, siltation, increase in cost of medicine and water treatment, extinction of flora and fauna and disruption of breeding ground for aquatic life. The study revealed sustainable measures that can be used in controlling wetland degradation to include the establishment of buffer zone around wetland; improvement in upland crop production, integration of local knowledge in wetland restoration, development of legal framework, and provision of accurate data on the dynamics of wetland. The study recommends public enlightenment and education on the value of wetland, monitoring and control of wetland resources exploitation and improved waste collection strategies as ways of preventing wetland degradations.*

Keywords: Wetland, Degradation, Sediment, Quality, Impact

INTRODUCTION

Wetlands have undergone great changes during the past decades due to the degradation of ecosystems, especially in urban areas where industrial effluents are on the increase and other challenges such as eutrophication associated with intensive agriculture (pesticides and herbicides) and also poor management of natural resources are reducing the quality of services expected of wetland area (Cvetkovic and Chow-Fraser, 2011; Shi et al., 2015). The degradation of wetland resources throughout the world is approaching an alarming level. Wetlands have been altered on a

global basis, as human society exploits the benefits provided by these natural systems. Extensive wetland resources in both industrialized and developing countries have already been lost or are undergoing frequent changes. These losses are as a result of conversion to intensive agriculture, or industrial use (including waste disposal) or through more gradual degradation as a result of hydrological perturbation, pollution, recreation pressure or increasing grazing and fishing activities (Turner, 2000). The impacts on wetland degradation are enormous and are very broad, and include direct losses through effects

on, biodiversity, the volume of water and extent of pollution, etc (Mitsch and Gosselink 2000). Therefore, the sustainability of these vital ecosystems depends on the maintenance of the value and health of wetland resources. Wetlands are characterized by soft, spongy soil or sediment/land saturated with draining or stagnant, fresh, brackish or salty water including marine with a shallow depth (at low tide) of not more than 6 m (RCS, 2016; Tariku & Abren 2023). Similarly, the Ramsar Convention (2016) defines wetlands as areas of marsh, fen, peat land or water, whether natural or artificial, permanent or temporary, with water that is static or flowing, fresh, brackish or salt, including areas of marine water the depth of which at low tide does not exceed six meters (Dugan, 1993).

Wetland ecosystems are important habitats which play vital roles as landscape elements, providing ecological, biogeochemical, hydrological and socio-economic benefits which are crucial for societal growth and development globally (Stuip et al., 2002). These functions can be realized through human interactions and are classified into direct use values like food, materials, recreational use etc. The indirect use values include flood control, groundwater recharge, shoreline stabilization, storm protection, water quality improvement and climate change mitigation among others.

Wetlands cover approximately 6% of the earth's surface (RCS, 2016; Tariku & Abren 2023) with diverse use values. For example, the water chemistry of wetlands is primarily a reflection of the geologic setting, water balance (relative proportions of inflow, outflow, and storage), and quality of inflowing water, type of soils and vegetation, and human activity within or near the wetland. In sub-Saharan Africa, the use of wetlands for agricultural production is increasingly considered as a potential solution to food security challenges in the region (UNEP, 2008; Rebelo et al., 2010). During periods of food shortage, wetlands can be the exclusive source of food for communities living within the areas (Rebelo et al., 2010). However, many wetlands in

sub-Saharan Africa are increasingly being degraded and lost due to agricultural expansion through drainage and conversion (Rebelo et al., 2010; Saunders et al., 2012). For instance, in Kenya, Owino and Ryan (2007) reported that approximately 50% area was loss in some papyrus wetlands over the period 1969–2000.

Wetland degradation leads to economic stagnation, Panayotou (1993) observes that such degradation is more pervasive in the developing world than high inflation, excessive foreign debt or economic stagnation. In the same line, Pearce (1993) concurs with Panayotou and supports the notion that “environmental damage costs developing countries approximately 5% of their Gross National Product (GNP). The introduction of heavy metals into the receiving water bodies and wetlands in the aquatic environment pose a major concern due to their persistent nature in the environment and the adverse effects on living organisms and humans through the food chains (Sabo *et al.*, 2013; Ayoade and Nathaniel, 2018). Sediments are free particles of soil found at the bottom of the aquatic environment in the form of clay, sand, organic material, or silt (Burton, 2002; Ingersoll *et al.*, 2002).

Sediments are essential elements of aquatic ecosystems because it supports both autotrophic and heterotrophic organisms (MacDonald *et al.*, 2003). Sediment plays crucial function in the nutrient cycle within the wetland ecosystem. According to (Ekhwan et al. 2009; Shiji, et al. 2015), sediments are responsible for the transportation of basic nutrients including pollutants. Sediments can become contaminated from various hazardous and toxic substances, including heavy metals (Harikumar et al. 2009). These metals can be conserved in sediments over long periods of time depending on their chemical components and their level of persistence including their biochemical characteristics of the substrata.

Major impacts of sediment contamination on the ecosystem are associated with contaminants that have direct effects on benthic communities and also on the upper trophic levels through food chain contamination (Burton, 2002). Contaminated sediment can cause lethal and sub-lethal effects on benthic and other sediment-associated organisms (USEPA 2001). Polluted sediment can reduce or eliminate species of recreational, commercial or ecological importance, either through direct effects or via the food supply chain. The knowledge and understanding of sediment quality of wetland serve as a veritable tool for monitoring environmental pollution in the ecosystem such as wetland areas. It also allows for wetland protection and restoration of the health status of such ecosystem's options (Aladesanmi *et al.*, 2016).

Apart from the natural process, metals can also enter into the aquatic system as a result of anthropogenic activities such as; agricultural activities, mining, effluents from industrial operations, disposal of municipal wastes among others (Shiji *et al.* 2015). Sediment contamination can also come from anthropogenic source, e.g., metals can enter into the ecosystem either by adsorbed onto suspended particles or in dissolved forms through runoff into water bodies (Remeikaitė-Nikienė, *et al.* 2018; Akoteyon and Kodja, 2022). Similarly, some heavy metals can gain access through atmospheric deposition (Remeikaitė-Nikienė *et al.*, 2018; Akoteyon and Kodja, 2022) while other can accumulate in bottom sediments with other components like organic matter (Dang, *et al.* 2015; Akoteyon and Kodja, 2022).

Considering the increasing threat resulting from anthropogenic and natural processes and the fragile, dynamic, and productive nature of wetland, there is the need for the monitoring of

wetland quality status for sustainable management.

CAUSES OF WETLAND DEGRADATION

The causes of wetland degradation have received attention in recent times due to the increasing disappearance of wetlands and the negative consequences on the population, the environment, flora and fauna, and the economy and including the overall effect on humans. According to Ahmad *et al.* (2019), wetlands have been degraded due to issues of climate change, encroachment by agricultural land use, rapid expansion of settlements through massive property development, human activities of living close to the wetlands, construction of dams for electricity supply, construction of drainage channels for domestic and industrial wastes into the wetlands thus, destroying its natural elements and many other factors.

Wetland ecosystems have been altered by a variety of natural stressors and human activities (USEPA, 2023). For several years, people have drained or filled wetlands for agriculture or development, causing habitat loss as well as a decline in many other important wetland functions. Human modifications such as stream channel, intensive groundwater withdrawal, introduction of pollutants, conversion for various uses, deforestation etc all have major ecological impact by altering the wetland ecosystem (USEPA, 2023). According to USEPA (2001) the degradation of wetland has resulted in decline of bird populations migrating over the Gulf of Mexico. Similarly, USEPA (2001) opined that human activities constitute a major cause of wetland degradation and loss by changing water quality, quantity, and flow rates; and changing species composition as a result of disturbance and the introduction of non-native species.

Kateregga and Magezi (2005) linked the causes of wetland degradation to inappropriate land use

practices, such as over exploitation of aquifers, increased agricultural activity, waste dumping, infilling for residential and industrial developments and destruction of wetland vegetation. Degradation of wetland is also occurring due to nutrient inputs from agricultural activities. Also, government policies such as wetland degradation through conversion to other use have also accelerated wetland degradation. Ghersi et al. (1992) observed that wetland program mission in Burkina Faso and Niger have resulted into the degradation of wetland in the Sahel due to the ignorance of the administration officials as well as those in charge of technical and political matters about the functions that wetlands perform. Panayotou (1993) attributed cities myopic planning horizons and high discount rates as a major cause of wetland degradation. Dugan (1990) observes that wetlands have been destroyed because society viewed their elimination as price to pay for the benefits of wetland conservation. Such perception has led to inappropriate management practices and wetland loss.

Swanson (1996) also noted that certain resources are perceived to be less worthy of attention for investment than others and such are destined for over exploitation and degradation. Many societies perceive wetlands as “wastelands” harboring disease carrying vectors and wastage of would-be agricultural land if drained. Dennis and Andrew (2005) observed that inappropriate farming techniques, resource extraction, unclear land ownership, population pressure and low levels of environmental awareness were important factors influencing wetland degradation.

Hirpo (2018), opined that intensive irrigation agriculture, the expansion of human settlement, industrial pollution, pesticides and fertilizers and water diversion for drainage and the construction of dams play major role in wetland degradation. Wetland conversion often results in water depletion, the displacement of populations, the

destruction of traditional production systems, habitat degradation, salinization, increases of waterborne diseases and other adverse ecological impacts (Yilma et al., 2003). Hence, the impact of wetland degradation is so integrated into different anthropogenic and climate issues that affect aquatic ecosystems especially the fishery and in order to develop and assure their continuity for the future, cost should be paid to understand the dilemmas that they face and in identifying the good practices which should be strengthened. Sugeb (2019) listed anthropogenic disturbance to catchment surfaces and hydrology, direct release of human waste products and draining of wetland for agricultural use, construction and infrastructural purposes as some of the factors responsible for wetland degradation.

Lack of adequate knowledge and awareness of the social, economic and ecosystem benefits of wetlands and the increasing demand for agricultural land due to population pressure and degradation of upland areas according to Afework and Teshome (2015) play significant role for increased conversion of wetlands. Poor policy formulation and implementation on the part of the government, and lack of a well-designed legal and institutional framework has also been identified as a key causative factor in wetlands degradation (Halls, 1997; Otubu, 2021). In addition, wetland deterioration has also been attributed to civil unrest, ignorance, poverty, governmental interference/proclamations, and lack of or ineffective wetland monitoring measures (Barasa et al., 2021).

Wetland are the most biologically productive part of the environment due to their moist conditions. In addition, they are a crucial component of the overall ecosystem since they are essential to the sustenance of the earth's surface and groundwater resources (Hardlife et al., 2014; Ajibola et al., 2016). Globally, wetlands make up between 5% and 8% of the earth's surface covering about 29.83 million km². It is estimated that wetlands in Asia

(9.2 million km²), South America (7.95 million km²), and North America (5.65 million km²) accounts for 78% of the global wetland while Africa has about 5.6 million km² which represents 19% of the global wetland (Carlos *et al.*, 2022). According to Loveline *et al.* (2015), Nigeria has a thriving wetlands environment that makes up 2.6% of the country's total area.

Nigeria is highly endowed with wetlands, particularly in the southern mangrove rain forests, which make up the largest portion of the national wetland resources (Aju & Aju 2021; Olaniyi, 2023). These can be found in the country's three geological zones, which are the South-South, South-West, and South-East. When viewed from the broad classification of wetlands, which may include the networks of major rivers that flow across several states of the north and south and their tributaries, lakes, the mangroves of the delta, streams, forests, etc., other areas in the northern part, like the North-Central as well as the North-East and North-West, also have one form of wetland or the other (Olalekan *et al.*, 2014).

The benefits of wetlands are numerous. These can be in the form of indirect benefits which accrue from the use of wetland and direct benefits emanating from the consumption of wetland resources. Wetland resources also have other values along the chain of use and utilization. According to Barbier *et al.* (1997) the benefits of wetland can be divided into social and economic values, therapeutic value and offer medicinal advantages through their favorable effects on lifestyle, mental and bodily well-being. Others include its role in creating value for utilities which foster intellectual advancement, their cultural significance, and their religious resonance for followers of many faiths and religions among other benefits.

SOCIOECONOMIC IMPACTS OF WETLAND DEGRADATION

Wetland provide food and habitat for a diverse array of plants and animals, act as buffers to flooding and erosion, and serve as key links in the global water cycle. Wetlands are among the most biologically productive ecosystems in the world. Their microbial activity enriches the water and soil with nutrients (Dahl, 2011). Plant growth in wetlands provides a “sink” for many chemicals including atmospheric carbon. Balwan and Kour (2021) noted that wetlands are among the most productive ecosystems in the world, comparable to rain forests and coral reefs. An immense biodiversity of species of microbes, plants, insects, fish, amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals can be part of a wetland ecosystem. Wetlands perform significant economic benefits to human society, including some ecosystem services that no other ecosystem can provide, including certain types of water quality improvement, flood protection, shoreline erosion control, and opportunities for recreation and aesthetic appreciation and natural products for human use at no cost. Wetland serves as reservoirs of substantial biodiversity in supporting numerous species from almost all the major groups of organisms from microbes to mammals (Dorney *et al.*, 2018).

Hirpo (2018) noted that wetland serve as source of water, food, feed, medicinal plants and other income generating activities for the rural community. They are vital in attracting tourists and providing ground for cultural ceremonies (Finlayson and Moser 1994). Wetlands also contribute to environmental wellbeing through recharging and discharging of underground water, hosting biological diversity, sequestering carbon, mitigating flood hazards, amongst others. In general, wetland resources contribute billions of incomes to the coffers of nations in various forms such as clean water, pure air, soil formation and protection, crop pest control, and provision of

food, fish, fuel, fiber, medicine, recreation, tourism, amongst others (Leykun, 2003). In urban areas, wetlands contribute to the livability of cities through improving the water quality, carbon sequestration, providing habitats for wildlife species. Regarding their economic significance, wetland resources have been investigated for use in agriculture (plant and animal husbandry, such as fishery, forestry, and poultry), land use, tourism (which generates foreign exchange),

commercial activities, provision of fuel wood for cooking and other uses, provision of scarce raw materials for pharmaceutical companies in the manufacture of drugs, SMEs and manufacturing industries, building materials, recycling, and irrigation. Although studies from advanced economies suggest that wetland resources contribute significantly to the national economy if appropriately identified and valued, the majority of wetland activities still take place in the informal sector, especially in developing nations like Nigeria where the value of wetland resources has been grossly undervalued (Ahmad and Shakeel., 2019).

Wetland ecosystem also contribute to the increase in property values and increase in economic and commercial activity along the real estate value chain (Otubu, 2021). Wetlands reduce global warming in an era when it has attracted attention from all across the world. The study of Cherono et al. (2018) provides similar benefits of wetland in terms of economic benefits, water provision, recreational amenities, socio-cultural values, nutritional benefits, medicinal properties, education and research purposes, flood control and air purification benefits.

Nijamir (2017) noted that wetland provides local people with raw materials for their small-scale local business. It was also opined that the local people relied on wetland as source of food e.g., fruits like pawpaw, plantain, banana, maize, cassava, and vegetables among many others.

Other raw materials derived from wetland includes but not limited to grass for making mats, pasture for animals, clay for brick-making, wood and timber from for construction and furniture. Wetland resources can be used as charcoal and firewood for cooking food by the locals as well as raw materials, among others. Local people who live close to the wetland use the water for domestic purposes, while farmers utilize its water for irrigation especially during dry seasons and in areas affected by drought which has increased significantly due to the impact of climate change. The locals use it for recreation, and the rich vegetation and animals provide enjoyment and tourism. Wetlands provide hunting and fishing opportunities to earn income.

Wetland offer water for transportation, and hydropower generation. In addition, other socioeconomic benefits of wetland areas include mitigation of floods, erosion control, and as a repository for genetic material production and regeneration, seed distribution, pollination, and the production of biomass that provides food and raw materials (Nijamir, 2017; Phethi & Gumbo, 2019). Were *et al.* (2019) opined that wetlands mitigate the consequences of climate change through the long-term collection and storage of atmospheric CO₂ sequestration through natural or artificial sinks. According to Sica *et al.* (2016), wetland helps in the filtration, purification, and detoxification of soils, and agricultural pollutants. Wetland areas inspire life-enriching activities, artistic, recreational, cultural, and spiritual roles, as well as education and research (Loveline *et al.*, 2015; Ajibola *et al.*, 2016).

The economic significance of the ecosystem in socio-economic activities cannot be over-emphasized. For example, the riparian forest ecosystems in Kenya are seen to have contributed to a large extent to food security, livelihoods and national economies through various activities including fisheries, water for irrigation, provision of wood materials and hydropower generation

(Kafumbata et al., 2014; Pörtner et al. 2021). Besides, the forests are recognized as areas of global diversity and thus, are named biodiversity hot spots (Ndalilo et al., 2020). It is adequate for ecosystem services such as regulation of water and soil quality assessment, minimization of the impacts of landscape disturbance on stream ecosystems (Rodriguez et al., 2017).

In modern times, the likely worst stage of soil degradation is linked to the rapid reduction in ecosystem services (Norman, 2022). Moreover, the negative impact of soil degradation leading to multiple economic influences, altering socio-demographic functions and at the same time hampering sustainable paths, particularly in a more ecologically fragile district for development is well understood (Helldén and Tottrup, 2008). In the reverse order, any given local system which experiences socio-economic developmental impact can as well influence the level of soil degradation leading to a negative multiplier effect that would need urgent attention. With these socio-ecological issues, human actions may tend to correct complexities caused by soil degradation through several measures one of which is the promotion of socio-environmental wellbeing in the affected areas.

In Africa, wetlands happen to be the main source of water and nutrients useful for biological productivity and usually help in the survival of local communities. Thus, sustainable management of wetlands remains critical to the long-term health, safety and welfare of many Africans (Schuyt, 2005). For example, the Nile River basin renders values to a range of wetland ecosystems with different spatial and institutional scales as well wetlands of different types contribute in different ways to the sustenance of millions of people (Awulachew, 2012). On the contrary, about 17% of the river wetlands and 20% of the inland flood wetlands in Africa have experienced degradation into non-wetlands and likewise, other wetland forms have been degraded

(Schuyt, 2005). Inland wetlands which are formed on flat to plain landscapes, depressions, banks and deltas of rivers (Ballanti et al., 2017), within margins of lakes, and where clayey soils are mostly found, usually have vital economic and environmental values (Clarkson et al., 2014).

There have been many studies on wetlands and their economic significance. Kumari et al. (2020) study the importance of wetlands for the ecosystem and their conservation based on the India perspective. They observe that wetlands cater for the needs of diverse biodiversity even though about 50% of these are lost globally. The study submit that management practices are required urgently to conserve the wetland system based on traditional knowledge to preserve ecosystem services in a more cost-effective way. Brander (2013) study the economic value of wetlands and observes that they support a large number of communities whether households or biodiversity. Accordingly, they provide economic service not only to people around but to those outside the vicinity of the wetland areas. The study also discusses the use and non-use economic values that wetlands provide.

MEASURES OF CONTROLLING WETLAND DEGRADATION

According to USEPA (2001), measures of controlling wetland degradation are many. It include; the act of conservation and restoration of wetlands on individual property, public support to local wetlands and watershed protection initiatives, public collaboration with local municipalities and state to develop laws and ordinances that protect and restore wetlands and encourage private acquisition of wetland for conservation purpose, Other methods include the encouragement of neighbors and developers to protect the function and value of wetlands, avoidance of wetland degradation during project construction, maintenance of wetlands and adjacent buffer strips as open space, reduction in

the amount of fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides applied to lawns and gardens. In addition, Kateregga and Magezi (2005) recommended measures such as the formulation of bye laws and guidelines for sustainable utilization of wetland resources.

SEDIMENT QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF WETLAND ECOSYSTEM

There abounds substantial literature on sediment quality assessment of wetland ecosystem. For example, Karbassi *et al.*, (2005) and Ezekiel *et al.* (2012), employed sediment cores to study the pattern of metals in wetland ecosystems across different parts of the world. Lawal-Are *et al.* (2017) examined heavy metal bioaccumulation in tropical water bodies while Adeleye *et al.*, (2018) employed palynological techniques to investigate recent surface sediments in the coastal area. Similarly, Sabo *et al.*, (2013), Temitope *et al.* (2016), Adisa and Adekoya (2016), Lawal-Are *et al.* (2017), Ayoade and Nathaniel (2018) reported high heavy metal contamination in sediments of the aquatic ecosystem above the prescribed regulatory guideline. Studies by Nobi *et al.* (2010), Ekaete *et al.* (2015) observed moderate to high concentrations of heavy metal contamination in sediments of wetland environment. Shiji *et al.* (2015) examined the surface sediment samples from various regions of Kavvayi Lake, Kerala using heavy metal analysis and phosphorous fractionation. Most of the techniques employed demonstrate the importance of multivariate statistical techniques in evaluating and characterizing data for identifying pollution sources in vulnerable sites. These findings from these studies show comparatively higher concentration of heavy metals above the background values.

Samar and Faezeh (2017) assessed heavy metals in surface sediments of Mighan wetland using sediment quality index. The findings showed that Copper contamination was higher compared to

other metals due to sewage from various sources such as; industrial, urban and agricultural and natural sources in the study area. Similarly, Tokatli (2017) investigated the sediment quality of Gala Lake with toxic elements using Pearson Correlation Index (PCI), Factor Analysis (FA), Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI), and Biological Risk Index, and Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques and reported that the PCI has significant positive correlations with the toxic elements at 0.01 significance level while the FA indicate agricultural and industrial factors responsible for the source of pollution in the study area. The RI revealed that cadmium was the significant element with the highest risk factors while nickel and chromium constitute the major risk factor for Biological Risk Index in the area.

Study by Dirisu *et al.* (2017) assessed the physico-chemical status of sediments in the Agbede Wetlands of Edo North catchment of Nigeria and noted that, nutrients of zinc, nickel and lead recorded in the area were of anthropogenic origin, while alkali metals and alkaline earth metals were from both anthropogenic and natural sources. The study argued that the contaminations of the wetland are derived from agricultural run-offs and geochemical weathering of the top soils. Hongmeng *et al.* (2019) investigated the distribution of nutrient elements in sediments with a view to assessing the ecological risk in the upper reaches of the Minjiang River watershed. The study revealed that the spatial distributions of nutrient elements in sediments of the upper reaches in Minjiang River Watershed were significantly affected by the local ecology and urban sewage discharge system.

Similarly, Tatenda *et al.* (2020) examined the distribution of metals and nutrients sediment depth and reported significant differences in nutrient and metal with high deterioration of sediment quality. The Pearson correlations employed suggest that most metals originated

from a similar source. The study provides baseline information for the management of wetland in relation to sediment metal pollution in the area. Pradit et al. (2022) examined the concentration and distribution of trace metals in sediment cores from the KhuanKhi Sian wetland, Thailand and noted an increase in sediment pollution from bottom to top of the sediment core. The sediment evaluation indices employed, i.e., EF and I-geo indicate moderate pollution of sediment from As.

Yang et al. (2023) employed principal component technique and wetland health index (WHI) to identify the important variables affecting the health of wetland condition in the Poyang Wetland in China and opined that the wetland near river mouths are characterized by poor condition. The WHI shows that the Poyang Lake wetland indicates fair condition. The study suggested the reduction of pollution from rivers as a critical measure for wetland protection in the area. Panda et al (2023) examined heavy metals in sediments from eight wetlands in India and noted that the mean values of Pb, Cr, and Cu in sediments exceeded the toxicity reference value. The relationship of the metals indicates high and moderate positive correlations between Cu and Zn and Pb and Cr.

The study demonstrates the link between heavy metals in wetland sediments and human cancer which can be used to make policies that limit human exposure to heavy metal contamination. Yongo et al. (2023) assessed heavy metal pollution in sediment from Changwang and Wuyuan Rivers in China and noted high concentrations of Cr, Co, Ni and Cu in Changwang River with elevated levels of As in Wuyuan River. The contamination factor, geo-accumulation index, and modified degree of contamination employed revealed that Changwang experienced considerable to very high heavy metal pollution, while Wuyuan had low to moderate pollution. The pollution load index demonstrated that the rivers were polluted

during all seasons. The risk index showed considerable and moderate risks in Changwang and Wuyuan, respectively while the sediment quality value indicate that Ni and Cr exceeded probable effect concentrations (PEC), indicating that the metals may cause toxic effects. The multivariate statistical technique used identified two sources of pollution.

The study provides valuable data to assess pollution risks and the management of riverine sediment quality. Khedr et al. (2023) examined the ecological risk and toxicity indices of heavy metals in the sediments of Upper Wadi El-Rayan Lake (UWRL) and Lower Wadi El-Rayan Lake (LWRL) in Egypt and reported that the ecological risk of the sediments of the two Lakes suffered varied degrees of metal pollution from Cd, Pb, and Ni. Cheng et al (2023) examined the spatial and temporal changes in the ecological quality of coastal wetlands of Linghekou using Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System based on PSR, AHP and InVEST methods for early warning on future ecological and environmental conditions. The study noted that the natural wetland area decreased with increased landscape fragmentation between 2005 and 2020.

The result of the composite indices of the Linghekou wetland in 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020 indicate decline from a sub-healthy state in 2005 to a sub-sick state in 2020 due to increasing interference from human activities and degradation of wetland ecological services. This study provides a scientific reference for coastal wetland management and ecological construction, and also enriches the research output on coastal wetlands. Wei et al. (2023) used the dense time series Sentinel-2 images to establish wetland database of the Yellow River Delta to analyze the spatial distribution and temporal changes in wetland during 2015–2022 and reported that the overall degree of landscape fragmentation in wetlands weakened with similar changes in the

number of patches and landscape shape index of the study area.

CONCLUSION

The current paper reviewed the socio-economic impacts of wetland degradation and noted that population explosion, climate change, anthropogenic activities, hydrological perturbation, and pollution among others contribute significantly to the current wetland degradation globally. The result of the review revealed the positive and negative impacts in the study area. Firstly, the review identified fuel wood, cultivation of food crop and vegetable and flood control in the urban area with significant socio-economic importance from tourism and recreation in the rural settlements. The review further revealed that poor conservation management practices, industrial revolution, mining and dredging activities, lack of accurate data, inconsistencies and poor enforcement of government policies and high poverty rate are major negative impacts resulting from wetland degradation. Furthermore, the review showed that, rise in water borne diseases, extinction of flora and fauna and disruption of breeding ground for aquatic life and siltation pose severe socio-

economic challenges to people who rely on wetlands for their livelihood. The review concluded that sustainable measures of controlling wetland degradation in the study area will require the establishment of buffer zone around wetland; improve upland crop production, integration of local knowledge in wetland restoration, development of legal framework, and provision of accurate data on dynamics of wetland. The review recommended the need for public enlightenment and education, monitoring and control of wetland resources exploitation and improved waste collection strategies for the sustenance of wetland ecosystem. The study provides baseline information on the dynamics of the socio-economic impacts of wetland degradation in Lagos with significant contribution literature.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) for the approval (Ref. No. LASU/VC/DSI/RP/23/020) and sponsorship of this research. We are also grateful to the management of the Lagos State University for the prompt release of the fund.

REFERENCES

- Adeleye, M. A., Adebayo, M. B. and Adeonipekun, P. A .2018.Palynological study of recent surface sediments from Coastal area of Lagos, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Science* 20(1), 199-205.
- Adisa, A. L. and Adekoya, J. A. (2016). Assessment of pollution by heavy metals in sediments of River Oyi and its tributary, Southwestern Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Science* 18(4), 871-886.
- Afework, Y. K and Teshome, T.T (2015).The Impact of Wetland Degradation and Conversion on Socioeconomic Values: The Case of Amhara National Regional State Tekuma Wetland, Lake Tana Sub-Basin, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Agriculture System (IJAS)*, 3 (1), 1-14.
- Ahmad, Z., Hussain, A. & Shakeel, A. (2019). Economics Importance of Wetlands, their Benefits and Values Case of Pakistan. Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, Islamabad. Munich Personal RePEc Archive (MPRA) Paper No. 95260. Retrieved from

<https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/95260/> - Date retrieved

Ajibola, M. O., Adeleke, A. M., & Ogungbemi, O. A. (2016). *An Assessment of Wetland Loss in Lagos Metropolis , Nigeria*. 6(7), 1–7. Journal name

Aju P. C. & Aju J. A. (2021). Mangrove forests in Nigeria: why their restoration, rehabilitation and conservation matters. *African Journal of Environment and Natural Science Research*, Aladesanmi, O.T., Agboola, F.K. and Adeniyi, I.F. 2016. Distribution of heavy metals in surface sediments from streams and their associated fishponds in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Health & Pollution*, 6(11):34-46.

Awulachew, S. B. (Ed.). (2012). *The Nile River Basin: water, agriculture, governance and livelihoods*. Routledge.

Ayoade, A. A. and Nathaniel, O. G. 2018. Assessment of heavy metals contamination of surface water and sediment of a tropical manmade Lake southwestern Nigeria. *International Journal of Environment and Pollution Research* 6 (3), 1-16.

Ballanti, L., Byrd, K. B., Woo, I., & Ellings, C. (2017). Remote sensing for wetland mapping and historical change detection at the Nisqually River Delta. *Sustainability*, 9(11), 1919.

Balwan, W.K and Kour, S (2021). Wetland-An Ecological Boon for the Environment. *East African Scholars Journal of Agriculture and Life Sciences*. 4(3), 38-48. DOI:10.36349/easjals.2021.v04i03.001

Barbier, E.B., Acreman, M. & Knowler, D. (1997). *Economic valuation of wetlands: A*

4(1), 84-93. Akoteyon, I.S (2022). Sediment quality assessment of Rivers Abesan and Owo in parts of Lagos, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Science*, 24(2), 306-322. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijss.v24i2.11> - Retrieval date

Akoteyon, I. S. and Kodja, D. J. (2022). Patterns of bottom sediment contamination in parts of River Ogun Lagos, Nigeria. *Environmental Issues* 9(1), 22-35.

guide for policy makers and planners. Ramsar Convention Bureau, Gland, Switzerland.

Brander, L., Brouwer, R., & Wagtendonk, A. (2013). Economic valuation of regulating services provided by wetlands in agricultural landscapes: A meta-analysis. *Ecological Engineering*, 56, 89-96.

Burton, G.A Jr. 2002. Sediment quality criteria in use around the world. *Limnology* 3(2), 65–75

Carlos, L., Herazo, S., Fern, G., Mar, L., & Betanzo-torres, E. A. (2022). Factors Affecting Wetland Loss: A Review. *Land*, 11, 434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11030434>

Cheng, Q.; Wang, T.; Chen, F. (2023). Study on the Spatial and Temporal Evolution of the Ecological Environmental Quality in Linghekou Wetland. *Sustainability*, 15, 7672. doi.org/10.3390/su15097672

Cherono, C.G., Hellen, I. & Okelo, O.P. (2018). Socio-Economic Benefits of Kingwal Wetland to the Local People. *Research & Reviews: Journal of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 6(4), 41-46.

Clarkson, M. O., Poulton, S. W., Guilbaud, R., & Wood, R. A. (2014). Assessing the utility of Fe/Al and Fe-speciation to record water column redox conditions in carbonate-rich sediments. *Chemical Geology*, 382, 111-122.

Cvetkovic, M., & Chow-Fraser, P. (2011). Use of ecological indicators to assess the quality of Great Lakes coastal wetlands. *Ecological Indicators*, 11(6), 1609-1622.

Dang, D.H., Lenoble, V., Durrieu, G., Omanović, D., Mullet, J.-U., Mounier, S. and Garnier, C., 2015. Seasonal variations of coastal sedimentary trace metals cycling: insight on the effect of manganese and iron (oxy)hydroxides, sulphide and organic matter. *Mar. Pollut.Bull.* 92 (1-2), 113-124,
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.12.048>.

Dahl, T.E. 2011. [Status and trends of wetlands in the conterminous United States 2004 to 2009](#). Washington, DC: U.S. Department of the Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service.

Dennis, K., & Andrew, M. (2005). The Effects of Wetland Degradation on the Socio Economic Welfare A case study of Nabisasiro Wetland in Rubaga division.

Dirisu A.R., Olomukoro J.O., Ezenwa I.M (2017). Physico-chemical trends in the sediments of Agbede Wetlands, Nigeria. *RMZ – M&G*, 64, 35–126. DOI 10.1515/rmzmag-2017-0009

Dorney, J., Savage, R., Adamus, P., & Tiner, R. (2018). *Wetland and Stream Rapid Assessments: Development, Validation, and Application*. London; San Diego, CA: Academic Press.

Dugan, P. (ed.). 1993. *Wetlands in danger: A world conservation atlas*. Oxford University Press, New York.

Ekaete, A. G., Ibironke, O. K., Olatunde, P. S. and Olaoye, O. P. 2015. Heavy metal pollutions and its associated ecological risks in Lagos Lagoon sediments, southwestern Nigeria. *American Chemical Science Journal* 9 (3), 1–13

Finlayson, C. M. (1994). *Monitoring Ecological Change In Wetlands*. pp. 163-180. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?title=Monitoring+Ecological+Change+in+Wetlands+of+Middle+Europe,+Stapfia&author=CM+Finlayson&publication_year=1994&

Gherzi, G., Grenon, E., & Ibrahim, L. (1992). Prospective studies and food strategies in the Sahel: the case of Niger. *Prospective studies and food strategies in the Sahel: the case of Niger*.

Halls, A.J. (ed.). (1997) *Wetlands, Biodiversity and the Ramsar Convention: The Role of the Convention on Wetlands in the Conservation and Wise Use of Biodiversity*. Ramsar Convention Bureau, Gland, Switzerland.

Harikumar, P.S., Nasir, U.P., & Rahman, M.P.M. 2009. Distribution of Heavy Metals in the Core Sediments of a Tropical Wetland System. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 6(2), 225-232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF03327626>

Hirpo, L. A. (2018). The Effect of Wetland Degradation on Fish Production in Ethiopia. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*, 5(2), 178–187. <https://doi.org/10.22192/ijarbs.2018.05.02.018>

Hongmeng Ye, Hao Yang , Nian Han , Changchun Huang , Tao Huang , Guoping Li , Xuyin Yuan and Hong Wang(2019) Risk Assessment Based on Nitrogen and Phosphorus Forms in Watershed Sediments: A Case Study of the Upper Reaches of

the Minjiang Watershed Sustainability, 11, 5565; doi:10.3390/su11205565

Ingersoll, C.G., Christopher, G. and Wenning, R.J. 2002. Use of sediment quality guidelines and related tools for the assessment of contaminated sediments: Executive Summary of a SETAC Pellston Workshop”. *Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*

Karbassi, A. R. and Bayati, G. R. N. B. I. 2005. Environmental geochemistry of heavy metals in a sediment core off Bushehr, Persian Gulf. *Journal of Environmental Health Science & Engineering* 2(4), 255-260.

Kateregga and Magezi (2005).The Effects of Wetland Degradation on the Socio Economic Welfare A case study of Nabisasiro Wetland in Rubaga division Kampala District © 2005 By Kateregga Dennis and Magezi Andrew. Available for download in Academia

Kumari, R., Shukla, S. K., Parmar, K., Bordoloi, N., Kumar, A., & Saikia, P. (2020). Wetlands conservation and restoration for ecosystem services and halt biodiversity loss: An Indian perspective. *Restoration of wetland ecosystem: a trajectory towards a sustainable environment*, 75-85.

Lawal-Are, A. O., Mokwenye, C. R. and Akinwunmi, M. F. 2017. Heavy metal bioaccumulation in *callinectes amnicola* and *farfantepenaeus notialis* from three selected tropical water bodies in Lagos, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Science* 19(2), 247-254. doi.org/10.4314/ij.s.v19i2.5.

Loveline, E. C., Biotechnology, N., Agency, D., & Road, A. (2015). International journal of environment. *International Journal of Environment*, 4(3), 177–184.

MacDonald, D.D., Ingersoll, C.G., Smorong, D.E., Lindskoog, R.A., Sloane, G. and Biernacki, T. (2003). Development and evaluation of numerical sediment quality assessment guidelines for florida inland waters. Florida Department of Environmental Protection, Tallahassee, Florida, 1-13.

Mitsch, W. J., & Gosselink, J. G. (2000). *Wetlands* (Fourth ed.). John Wiley.ra

Ndalilo, L., Wekesa, C., & Mbuvi, M. T. (2020). Indigenous and local knowledge practices and innovations for enhancing food security under climate change: examples from Mijikenda communities in coastal Kenya. *Sustainability Challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa II: Insights from Eastern and Southern Africa*, 63-82.

Nijamir, K. (2017). Socio-economic impact of wetlands : a study based on Navithanveli DS Division. *World News of Natural Sciences*, 14, 116–123.

Nobi, E. P., Dilipan, E., Thangaradjou, T., Sivakumar, K. and Kannan, L. 2010. Geochemical and geo-statistical assessment of heavy metal concentration in the sediments of different coastal ecosystems of Andaman Islands, India. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 87 (2), 253–264

Norman, L. M., Lal, R., Wohl, E., Fairfax, E., Gellis, A. C., & Pollock, M. M. (2022). Natural infrastructure in dryland streams (NIDS) can establish regenerative wetland sinks that reverse desertification and strengthen climate resilience. *Science of the Total Environment*, 849, 157738.

Olalekan, E.I., Abimbola, L.M. Saheed, M. & Damilola, O.A. (2014). Wetland Resources of Nigeria: Case Study of the Hadejia-Nguru Wetlands. *Poultry, Fisheries & Wildlife Sciences*,

2(2).Retrieved from
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2375-446X.1000123>

Olaniyi, A.O. (2023). Analysis of Mangrove Forest Resources in Nigeria for State Specific Restoration Policy. *Science World Journal*, 18(1), 106-113.

Otubu, A. K. (2021). Quest for Housing and Preservation of Wetlands in Nigeria: A Case Study of Lagos State. *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy*, 3 (3), 146-152.

Owino, A. O., & Ryan, P. G. (2007). Recent papyrus swamp habitat loss and conservation implications in western Kenya. *Wetlands Ecology and management*, 15, 1-12.

Panda, B. P., Mohanta, Y. K., Paul, R., Prusty, B. A. K., Parida, S. P., Pradhan, A., ... & Sarma, H. (2023). Assessment of environmental and carcinogenic health hazards from heavy metal contamination in sediments of wetlands. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 16314.

Panayotou, T (1993); *Green Markets, The Economics of Sustainable Development*, Institute for contemporary studies, San Francisco, California.

Pearce David, W., Warford, Jeremy J., 1993. *World Without End: Economics Environment and Sustainable Development*. Oxford University Press (published for the World Bank).

Phethi, M. D., & Gumbo, J. R. (2019). Assessment of impact of land use change on the wetland in Makhitha village, Limpopo province, South Africa. *Jamba: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 11(2), 1–6.
<https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v11i2.693>

Pörtner, H. O., Scholes, R. J., Agard, J., Archer, E., Arneth, A., Bai, X., ... & Ngo, H. T. (2021).

IPBES-IPCC co-sponsored workshop report on biodiversity and climate change. *IPBES and IPCC*, 10.

Pradit, S.; Noppradit, P.; Jitkaew, P.; Sengloyluan, K.; Kobkeatthawin, T.; Laerosa, A.; Sirivithayapakorn, S. (2022). Heavy Metal Contamination and Ecological Risk Assessment in the Sediment Cores of the Wetlands in Southern Thailand. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.*, 10, 1921.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse10121921>

Ramsar Convention Secretariat (2016) The fourth Ramsar strategic plan 2016–2024.

Ramsar handbooks for the wise use of wetlands, 5th edition, vol. 2. Ramsar Convention Secretariat, Gland, Switzerland

Rebelo, L.M., McCartney, M. P., and Finlayson, C. M. (2010). Wetlands of Sub-Saharan Africa: distribution and contribution of agriculture to livelihoods. *Wetlands Ecol. Manag.* 18, 557–572.

Remeikaitė-Nikienė, N., Garnaga-Budrė, G., Lujanienė, G., Jokšas, K., Stankevičius, A., Malejevas, V. and Barisevičiūtė, R. 2018. Distribution of metals and extent of contamination in sediments from the south-eastern Baltic Sea (Lithuanian zone). *Oceanologia* 60(2), 193-206

Rodríguez-Arias, C.E.; Silva Benavides, A.M. (2017). Los Humedales de la Quebrada Estero en San Ramón, Costa Rica: Importancia y estado actual. *Posgrado Sociedad Revista Electrónica Sistema Estudios Posgrado*, 15, 13–26.

Sabo, A., Gani, A. M. and Ibrahim, A. Q. 2013. Pollution Status of Heavy Metals in Water and Bottom Sediment of River Delimi in Jos, Nigeria. *American Journal of Environmental Protection* 1 (3), 47-53. DOI:10.12691/env-1-3-1

- Samar, M and Faezeh S. (2017). Heavy Metals Assessment of Surface Sediments in Mighan Wetland Using the Sediment Quality Index. *ECOPERSIA* 5 (2), 1761-1770.
- Saunders, M. J., Kansime, F., and Jones, M. B. (2012). Agricultural encroachment: implications for carbon sequestration in tropical African wetlands. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 18, 1312–1321.
- Schuyt, K. D. (2005). Economic consequences of wetland degradation for local populations in Africa. *Ecol. Econ.* 53, 177–190.
- Shi, L, Wu, P. Wang, Y., Sun, S., and Liu, J. (2015) Assessment of water stress in Shaanxi Province based on crop water footprint. *Chin J Eco-Agric* 23(5):650–658
- Shiji, M., Kavya, P. and Harikumar, P.S.P (2015) Sediment Quality Assessment of Kavvayi Wetland in South Coast India with Special Reference to Phosphate Fractionation and Heavy Metal Contamination. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 6, 1308-1321. doi.org/10.4236/jep.2015.611114
- Sica, Y. V., Quintana, R. D., Radeloff, V. C., & Gavier-Pizarro, G. I. (2016). Wetland loss due to land use change in the Lower Paraná River Delta, Argentina. *Science of the Total Environment*, 568, 967–978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.04.200>
- Stuip, M.A.M., Baker, C.J. and Oosterberg, W. (2002). *The Socio-economics of Wetlands*: published by Wetlands International and RIZA, and printed by Grafiko, Wageningen, the Netherlands Lannas, K. S. M., and J. K. Turpie. (2009). Valuing the provisioning services of wetlands: contrasting a rural wetland in Lesotho with a peri-urban wetland in South Africa. *Ecology and Society* 14(2), 18.
- Swanson T.M. (1996); *The Economics of Environmental Degradation Tragedy for the Commons*.
- Tatenda Dalu, Rolindela Tshivhase 1, Ross N. Cuthbert , Florence M. Murungweni and Ryan J. Wasserman (2020) Metal Distribution and Sediment Quality Variation across Sediment Depths of a Subtropical Ramsar Declared Wetland . *Water* , 12, 2779; doi:10.3390/w12102779
- Tokatli, C. (2017) Bioecological and statistical risk assessment of toxic metals in sediments of a worldwide important wetland: Gala Lake National Park (Turkey) (2017). *Archives of Environmental Protection* 43(1), 34–47. DOI 10.1515/aep-2017-0007
- Turner, R.; van den Bergh, J.C.J.M.; Söderqvist, T.; Barendregt, A.; van der Straaten, J.; Maltby, E.; van Ierland, E.C. (2000). *Ecological-Economic Analysis of Wetlands: Scientific Integration for Management and Policy*. *Ecol. Econ.* 35, 7–23
- UNEP (2008). *Africa: Atlas of our Changing Environment*. Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).
- USEPA (2001). United States Office of Water EPA 843-F-01-002d Environmental Protection Office of Wetlands, September 2001 Agency Oceans and Watersheds (4502T).
- United States Environmental Protection Agency, (EPA) (2023). United States Environmental Protection Agency (2023). *Wetlands: What are the trends in the extent and condition of wetlands and their effects on human health and the environment?* Available online at <https://www.epa.gov/report-environment/wetlands>

Wei, C.; Guo, B.; Lu, M.; Zang, W.; Yang, F.; Liu, C.; Wang, B.; Huang, X.; Liu, Y.; Yu, Y.; et al. (2023). The Changes in Dominant Driving Factors in the Evolution Process of Wetland in the Yellow River Delta during 2015–2022. *Remote Sens.* 15, 2858. doi.org/10.3390/rs15112858

Yang, W.; Zhong, J.; Xia, Y.; Hu, Q.; Fang, C.; Cong, M.; Yao, B.; You, Q. A Comprehensive Multi-Metric Index for Health Assessment of the Poyang Lake Wetland. *Remote Sens.* 2023, 15, 4061. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15164061

Were, D., Kansiime, F., Fetahi, T., Cooper, A., & Jjuuko, C. (2019). Carbon Sequestration by Wetlands: A Critical Review of Enhancement Measures for Climate Change Mitigation. *Earth Systems and Environment*, 3(2), 327–340. https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-019-00094-0

Yilma, D. and Geheb, K. (Eds). (2003). Wetlands of Ethiopia: Proceedings of a seminar on the resources and status of Ethiopia's wetlands. pp.1, 5, 13.

Yongo, E.; Jin, F.; Mutethya, E.; Wu, D.; Zhang, P.; Guo, Z. (2023). Sediment Heavy Metal Pollution Assessment in Changwang and Wuyuan Rivers in Hainan Island, China. *Water*, 15, 1580. doi.org/10.3390/w15081580